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“UNTIL WHEN?”

It was a dreary night
When I was coping in the dark
Exhausted, weak, and tired
Inside the labyrinth so tight

Until when is my question
I can't endure my boredom
My painful back with laceration
Searching for a remediation

Why do I keep deciphering
Your reasons for everything
I can't derive the true meaning
Why did you let this happening

I am not in a position
To question your proposition
My only goal is for protection
Of my shriveled body in motion

To end this poem with a question
That I want you to ponder on
Open your eyes and just move on
Until when will you go on?